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ISSUES ON ISLAMIC MARRIAGE AND GUARDIANSHIP IN NIGERIA AND SOLUTIONS THERE TO: LESSON FROM MOROCCO AND INDIA

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ABSTRACT

In Islamic Law, marriage 'Nikah' is referred to as a civil contract between a man and a woman. Traditionally, the word guardian (Wali) means a person who extends help. According to Islamic law, a wali or guardian is a person who has the authority to enter into contract on behalf of a minor or an insane person and or solemnizes a women's marriage during her Nikah. A Wali also serves as an adviser to the bride in all her life affairs and the same thing applies when it comes to choosing her life partner. The aims and objectives of this research paper are: to determine who can be a guardian as regards to marriage under Islamic Law, to determine the extent of the powers of a guardian regards to Islamic marriage contract, whether his absence can violate the marriage, to determine the extent of abuse of the institution of marriage guardianship; and finally to proffer remedial measures. This paper examined issues related to Islamic marriage guardianship in Nigeria. The paper also considered the necessity to have a guardian in Islamic marriage contract where he is absent the marriage is a nullity ab initio. It equally examined the extent to which partners or guardians abuses the institution of marriage guardianship. The paper

adopts both doctrinal and non-doctrinal research methodology being an arm-chain legal research. The paper finally recommended that issues related to marriage guardianship under Islamic Law be codified and a legislation to be passed by the State Houses of Assembly in the federation. It is also a part of our recommendation that District Heads, Village Heads and Emirs be given powers to act as marriage guardians subject to judicial review. It is also recommended that where a guardian acted ultra-vires or refused to act, sanction be prescribed. Finally, it is recommended that where a lady is matured, she should have the liberty to choose who should be her guardian from amongst the hierarchy of guardians, except her biological father who has power of Ijibar over her.

Keywords: Issues, Islamic Marriage, Guardianship, in Nigeria, lesson from Morocco & India.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In Islamic Law, marriage “Nikah” is referred to as a civil contract. Wali is an Arabic word meaning guardian, custodian, protector or helper. A Wali is the bride’s lawful guardian who is responsible for the bride’s life prior to marriage. It is his duty to ensure that the proposed groom is a reliable and trustworthy person who will continue to carry on with his role and responsibility towards the bride after marriage.

Traditionally, the word guardian (Wali) means a person who extends help. According to Islamic Law, a Wali is a person who has the authority to enter into contract on behalf of a minor or an insane person and give consent and solemnizes a woman’s marriage for her during Nikah². There is a close bond of love and affection between the bride and her Wali, in the Muslim family structure to the extent that marriage is to be solemnized by Wali on behalf of bride. Also, the wali serves as an adviser to the bride in all her life affairs.

One of the problems directly connected with the condition of marriage is Marriage Guardianship or Waliyat Al-Nikah. This is a very complex problem, let attempt to clarify it and see the insights of the social structure it may give. Simply stated, Marriage Guardianship is the legal authority invested in person who is fully qualified and competent to safeguard the interest and rights of another who is incapable of doing so independently.¹ The role of A Marriage Guardian may be defined as a duty assigned to him by law and by virtue of his responsibility for the ward’s welfare. If guardianship is defined as a right of the guardian, as some writers seem inclined to do, and if the right can be conceived without corresponding duties, the Guardian is depicted as a person endowed with coercive rather than advisory power.² However, in spite of these precaution, negligence and abuse do occur

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¹ Abdul-afi: Marriage Guardianship, Dr. Farookq’s study Resources page, American Trust Publications 1977 pg. 70

² Ibid

and guardians do make unwise decisions. Deliberate negligence and or abuse is forbidden³

These abuses often do occur for economic or personal benefit of the guardian. For example, in 2006 a Yemeni study on early marriage reported huge age gaps between the spouses, and the press noted that among the reasons behind early marriage is that the parents are lured into marrying their daughters off at young age by the rich men proposing to marry their daughters.⁴

Having this back ground in mind, the paper adopts an arm chair method in conducting this work. It succinctly begins by defining the word guardian both literally and technically and types of guardian. Terms and conditions of becoming Wali is thoroughly discussed in the paper than adumbrates order of Guardian.

The persons who must have a guardian in the conduct of their marriages are adequately outlined. The role of a marriage guardian is also itemized in the paper. It narrates juristic view on the issue of Guardianship, the paper then makes a general survey into other jurisdictions by bringing the position contained in their respective codes as applied in judicial authorities. It also gives, how a minor spouse can repudiate a marriage contract entered into by his/her Wali upon attaining majority.

In this Article one is expected to adopt a methodology that is suitable for achieving a good result. There are basically two approaches to legal research. They are doctrinal and non-doctrinal legal research. Doctrinal research entails collection of data for the work from authorities and sources of law such as the constitution, statutes, law reports, subsidiary legislation, judicial decision etc. this article intend to rely on (some of) them. The non-doctrinal sources include legal text books on law, official reports, non-official reports, internet sources etc. The article intends to draw data from any or some of them relevant to it. Data so collected would be subjected to critical assessment on the basis of qualitative analysis.

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⁴Lynn Wlchman, a comparative overview of textual development and advocacy Amsterdam, University press, 2007, retrieved in university press, 2007, retrieve in WWW.Oen. Org/download typ= document and Docid = visited on 27/9/14, 2:04pm

This article intends to examine guardianship as regards to marriage under Islamic Law or Waliyat Al-Nikah in order to achieve result from what the following research questions:

- i. Who is a guardian as regards to marriage under Islamic Law?
- ii. Whether a guardian is necessary in Islamic Marriage contract such that his absence can vitiate the marriage itself?
- iii. Whether the institution of marriage guardianship is being abused in conducting marriage under Islamic Law?
- iv. What remedial measures are there to meet the challenges?

1.1 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

Aims and objectives of the research Article are:

- i. To determine who can be a guardian as regards to marriage under Islamic Law.
- ii. To determine the extent of powers of a guardian as regards to Islamic marriage contract, whether his absence can vitiate the marriage.
- iii. To determine the extent of abuse of the institution of marriage guardianship; and
- iv. To proffer remedial measures.

2.0 DEFINITION OF WALI

The word Wali is taken from the Arabic word Al-Wilayah, meaning the willingness to take responsibilities to manage or to take up the authority to administer something such as managing the orphans by attending to their needs and to become a Wali for a woman by performing a marriage contract for her.⁵

Technically the word Wali refers to two things: -

From the language perspective, the willingness to act or manage or the authority to administer something

From the terminology perspectives, someone who possess or has been granted authority to perform a marriage contracted.⁶

Having defined the word Wali both literally and technically in the paragraphs above, it is discernable that the work of this write will be limited to the second meaning which is the technical one. Having in mind the definition of Wali as it affects marriage contract.

⁵Wali (guardian) in Islam, WWW. Islam.my/stes/default/file/wali-in Islam, visited on 22nd /09/2014 06:14 pm

⁶ Ibid pg 2

3.0 TYPE OF WALI

Wali can be categorized into 2 types;

- i. Wali Mujbir (Guardian by force), and
 - ii. Wali Ikhtiar
- i. WALI MUJBIR: Is regarded as the perfect Wali because he has full power to endorse a marriage on behalf of everyone under his care. Although a father may marry off his virgin daughter without her consent, it is Sunnah (favourable) for the father to request for her consent. The father may not act freely using his Ijbar authority. He has to make sure that his action is just and fair for the benefit of his daughter. That is why Islam has enforced 3 conditions which allow for the Ijbar authority of the father to be enforced upon his daughter:
- a. There is no apparent dispute between father and daughter
 - b. The groom must be suitable for the daughter
 - c. The prospective husband is capable of paying the Dowry (Mahr) immediately.⁷

Although many Muslim jurists do not subscribe to this idea of power of Ijbar, Maliki jurists validates it ⁸ In the case of a daughter who is a Widow or Divorcee, the father cannot force her into a marriage unless by a clear and undisputed permission as explained in the Hadith by Darul Qudni of which the prophet (Peace and blessing be upon him) which explained the that a

“A widowed has more right unto herself than her guardian and a virgin woman is married out as wife by her Guardian”⁹

From the above definition, we can see therefore, that a Wali is a person who has power to force his daughter into marriage notwithstanding her refusal to go into the marriage as approved by Maliki school. With the current wind of changes and the influence occasion by Western Culture and education into our society, it will be desirable to allow a lady who has come of age to choose her prospective husband unless her choice will work against her welfare.

⁷ ibid

⁸ ibid

⁹ ibid

ii. WALI IKHTIAR is a Wali from Asabah, i.e guardian related to a woman with authority to marry her out with her consent. Wali Ikhtiar includes a Wali Akhrab and Abad who are Wali in the absence of Wali Mujbir who is either the father or grandfather from the father's side. Such wali can marry off mature adult women and does not have any authority to force any marriage contract.¹⁰

Wali Ikhtiar may only marry off a bride after she has given her consent. The consent may be given in two ways:

For widowed/divorced women, she must provide her consent clearly and verbally, her consent in silence alone is not sufficient by virtue of her circumstance.¹¹

The prophet (peace and blessing be upon him) says; "It is Sunnat for a father to ask permission from a virgin woman, and her silence is her consent"¹² (by Imam Muslim).

From the above therefore Wali Ikhtiar can be seen as a person authorize to marry off a Bride in the absence of her father or Grandfather or delegated by them, who has no power to force her into the marriage.

Having seen the types of Wali in Islam as it affects marriage contract, let's go further to see the term and condition for becoming a Wali in Islamic Marriage contract.

4.0 TERMS AND CONDITIONS TO BECOME A WALI

The terms and conditions are as follows:

A male who has reached puberty and mature

A Muslim, a just person and not Fasiq (someone who violates Islamic law)

Not in inhar; A freeman (not slave or in bondage)

Has no visual impairment (due to old age) which may impair eye sight¹³

5.0 PERSONS ENTITLED TO GUARDIANSHIP IN MARRIAGE

The following persons can act as Guardians to a Marriage Contract

a) Father b) Paternal grandfather how high/low whatsoever,

c) Brother or other male member of the father's family.

¹⁰ ibid

¹¹ ibid

¹² Ibid

¹³ Ibnrushi, BidayatulMujtahidWanihatayatulMuqtasid, KistabuluNikah published by DarulFikr 2001, Vol. II Pgg11

d) Maternal uncle, or other maternal relation¹⁴

An analysis of the above mentioned persons entitled to guardianship in the marriage contract and on the order of Guardianship in term of preference.

6.0 ORDER OF GUARDIANS

Order of Wali in a Muslim marriage is requirement that must be taken into account by all parties either couple who are getting married, the parents, and those directly involved in the wedding arrangements such as the Imams. The order of Wali is as follows:

- a) Biological father
- b) Grandfather from the father's side, or older
- c) A male sibling of the same father and mother
- d) A male sibling of the same father
- e) A nephew from the father's side of the same father and mother, or younger
- f) A nephew from the father side or younger
- g) A male siblings of the same father
- h) An uncle from the father's side of the same father and mother, or younger
- i) Uncle from the father's side of the same father
- j) A nephew from an uncle from the father's side of the same father and mother (cousin)
- k) Father's uncle of the same father (distant grandfather)
- l) Father's uncle of the same father (distant grandfather)
- m) A nephew from father's uncle of the same father and mother (second cousin)
- n) A nephew from father's uncle of the same father or younger (second cousin)
- o) Grandfather's uncle of the same father and mother
- p) Grandfather's uncle of the same father
- q) A son of the grandfather's uncle of the same father and mother, or younger
- r) A son of the grandfather's uncle of the same father or younger
- s) Judge/King Guardian (Wali Hakim)
- t) Wali Tahkim (for a state without a Wali Hakim), and

¹⁴Guardianship in marriage [WWW.Madinah Mosque. Cardiff. Org. uk/Muslim-law-of-marriage.Pdf](http://WWW.MadinahMosque.Cardiff.Org.uk/Muslim-law-of-marriage.Pdf) visited on 22nd /09/2014

u) Al-Mutiq, a Master who has freed his woman slave.¹⁵

In practice however, one can see that this preference is hardly given consideration for people nowadays are prepared to delegate their closer family friends as Wali to their ward. It is hereby suggested that it is proper to adhere to the above order.

7.0 MARRIAGE BY WALI HAKIM

For the woman who does not have Wali Nasab (from her own kinship) or has problems with her Wali, she is allowed to refer to a Judge/King Guardian (Wali Hakim) because a king is a wali to those who do not have one as indicated in the Hadith by the prophet (peace and Blessing be upon him) where he was reported to have said:

“Sultan/King is the guardian for those who do not have guardian”

(Ahmad and Ashabu Sunna Al-Arba’ah Aisha).¹⁶

A woman who has problems with her Wali to get married will require Wali Hakim under the following conditions:

- a. Wali refuses
- b. Wali disappears/lost
- c. Wali for convert
- d. Wali for an illegitimate child
- e. Wali for a woman who does not have Wali Nasab¹⁷

It is therefore noted from the above that Wali Hakim only operates in some exceptional circumstances, in the case of a woman who does not have Wali Nas’ab like a new convert to Islam or where the Wali refuses to give his consent and it is a subject before a judge, and Imam or any person authorized to act as such.

8.0 REQUIREMENT FOR WALI'S CONSENT

The requirement for a Wali’s consent in a marriage have been stated in Qur’an and Sunnah. A verse from the Holy Qur’an on the issue of Wali states that “...Therefore you may marry

¹⁵Wali (Guardian) in Islam (supra) P.g 7

¹⁶Wali Gordian in Islam (supra)

¹⁷ Sura an Nisa (4) verses 25 Abdullah Yusuf Ali. The Holy Qur’an arabix text and English translation of the meaning of selected commentaries saba Islamic Media Kuala Lumpur.

¹⁸ Al-Tirmidhi, Sunan Al-Tirmidhi, Kitab Al-Nikah (Beirut: Dar Al-aharab al-islam, 1981) vol. 2 pp. 398

¹⁹ bdipg 7-8

them with the permission of their guardian and then their dowry so that they may live a decent life in wedlock”.

In another verse it is stated:

“...And Allah is most knowing about your faith. You (believers) are of one another. So, marry them with the permission of their people and give them their due compensation according to what is acceptable. They should be chaste, neither (of) those who commit unlawful intercourse randomly nor those who take (secret) lovers...”¹⁷

In both verses cited, it is clearly mentioned that permission of wali is obligatory.

The principle of wali was also stated in the hadith as an obligatory element for solemnization of marriage. It is narrated from Aisha (R.A) that the Prophet (SAW) said:

“The marriage of a woman who marries without the consent of her guardian is void. He (SAW) said these words three times.”²⁰

However, Muslim jurists from different schools of thought bear varying opinions on the consent of the wali in marriage. The Shafi’i, Maliki and Hanbali jurists opines that the consent of wali is compulsory for the solemnization of marriage, While the Hanafi jurist consider the consent of the wali merely as a condition for a valid marriage. Imam Shafi’i said: “if a woman marries without the consent of her guardian, her marriage is void”. He relied on the Qur’an verse 25 of Suratul Nisa (chapter four of the Holy Qur’an).

The Maliki jurists emphasize on the importance of the consent of wali for a woman in her first marriage. And later, she is allowed to freely enter into her second marriage.²¹

9.0 WHO MUST HAVE A GUARDIAN IN MARRIAGE

Here, different positions have been taken by different schools of law. The general view however, is that, minors, insane, and inexperienced irresponsible persons of either sex must have marriage guardian¹⁸ yet the Law Books focus on the women’s need for Guardianship and little is said about the need of men. This may be due to the fact that men are generally believed to be relatively more experienced than women and tend to marry

²⁰ Muhammad Ifzai Mahmood and Noraini Binti Md Hashim: Marriage without Wali’s consent: A paradigm shift’s in the family structure of Pakistan by 29(SI) 2021 IIUM 135-151 <http://journals.IIUM.Edu.my> accessed on 26th September, 2023

²¹Abdul-Afi H. (SUPRA)

their juniors in which case two basic reasons for Guardianship, i.e. minority and experience are eliminated. It is the woman who is usually said to lack experience in practical affairs and hence, may be tricked into commitments contrary to her interests. Moreover, if she contracts marriage on her own behalf, she may give the impression of being inconsiderate, presumptuous and inclined to intermingle with men unnecessarily, action which would customarily stigmatize her character.

For such reasons the jurists argue, that a Guardian is required to protect the woman's interest, to safeguard her moral integrity and to take all possible precautions to maximize the probability of a successful marriage. And because, the father's love and care for his daughter are usually not taken for granted, he is the first man to qualify as her guardian provided, of course, that he meets the other requisites of Guardianship.¹⁹

Difference of opinion as to what constitutes a woman's lack of experience which endangers her moral integrity has led to different views on the conditions under which a woman needs a marriage guardian. These views are as follows:²⁰

- i. Woman who's such Marriage contracts are invalid unless the woman involved has a guardian to represent her. She cannot give herself or anyone else in marriage, nor can she appoint a representative other than her lawful guardian. This applies to every woman irrespective of her age, physical conditions and material status i.e. whether she is a Spinster, Widow or Divorcee.
- ii. If the Guardian so authorizes, a woman may give herself and others in marriage and may also appoint any representative she wishes.

This assumes that the guardian trusts her judgment and is reasonably confident that her interest will be protected. In the absence of such authorization, a marriage guardian is necessary.

- iii. Immaturity and minority, a woman, maiden or otherwise who is mentally sound and has reached the age of puberty may independently negotiate marriage contracts and give herself or others in marriage. If her chosen man turns out to be unsuitable, or if she accepts a dowry less than that of her equals, the guardian may object to her choice and request

¹⁹WWW. Global web post/frooqm/studies-re/islam/gender/marriage-Wali.htm last visited 22/9/2014 at 7:12pm

²⁰ ibid

annulment of the contract. Any unjustified objection on his part can be overruled by the legal authorities upon the woman's request. But if he raises no objection her choice and marriage are valid.

iv. A woman who is in the approved state of mind and physical growth is free to negotiate contract and give herself in marriage. No guardian has any right to object to her choice, whatever the choice may be.

v. VIRGINITY (MAIDENNESS): If a woman is a virgin she cannot marry without a guardian. But if she is a widow or divorcee, she may marry independently and make her own arrangements.

vi. NOBILITY AND WEALTH If a former slave girl or a poor woman of low rank appoint an agent to represent her in marriage that is seemly and advisable. But if she acts on her own behalf, her marriage is valid. On the other hand, a noble woman of wealth and high status must be represented in marriage by a guardian or a community official. This view is probably taken because such a woman has much to lose if she is not well-advised.²¹

Obviously, all shade of opinions on this question are represented. It is important to note that each side tries to support its position with authority. It is to note that the main concern of all parties is the protection of the moral integrity as well the material interest of the woman involved. In the opinion of some jurists, it is in her best interest to have a marriage guardian. Other jurists prefer she acts independently but with the careful guidance of a guardian. Still others consider it best to allow her act freely without supervision.

These difference in opinions arose not from a disagreement on the underlying principles of law but rather on the interpretation of certain texts and the application of certain principles.²² The Qur'an and the other sources of law involved in support of the various arguments are held by all parties as binding. But the interpretation of the texts or the application of the principles is another matter which is largely determined by the jurists' personal discretion.²³

²¹ ibid

²² Infra

²³ ibid

10.0 THE ROLE OF A MARRIAGE GUARDIAN

The role of a marriage Guardian may be defined as a right conferred on him by the law, empowering him to act on his own behalf with or without regard for her wishes. It may also be considered as a duty assigned to him by the law and by virtue of his responsibilities for the wards welfare. If Guardianship is defined as a right of the guardian as some writers seem inclined to do, and if rights can be conceived without corresponding duties, the guardian is depicted as a person endowed with coercive rather than advisory powers.²⁴ He is primarily interested in preventing any match that may bring dishonor to the family or tribe. In view of a particular relationship between a kinsman Guardian who is often the father and his ward, and keeping in mind Islam's opposition to the tribal conception of honour and its own advocacy of brotherhood and equality. It is unlikely that Guardianship was endorsed for reason other than the welfare of the ward.

It is of course conceivable, perhaps even imperative, that the guardian should consider the ward's interests as his own. Thus when he acts on the matter he may appear as if he were defending his interests while, in fact he is defending those of his ward.²⁵

A contemporary writer has noted that it is first the kindred and secondly, the woman herself, who must be protected from a misalliance, but in no case shall the guardian derive any material advantage or consider anything but the best interest of the ward. If he does so, his action, according to all school, will be Haram (forbidden). Authorities of all Schools of law are in accordance with some writers, unanimous in characterizing Marriage guardian as the right to assist a woman at her marriage.²⁶

Muslim jurists who insist on marriage guardianship seem to consider it a duty rather than a right of the guardian, or at least a synthesis of both. While a Guardian has the right to negotiate and conclude a marriage on his ward's behalf and to give his consent or objection to her unwise choice. It is his duty to exercise this right in her best interest. To fulfill this duty, he must have the right to participate in the decision making process and avail of his experience in helping her.

²⁴WWW.Golbalweb (supra)

²⁵ Ibid

²⁶ ibid

However, in spite of these precautions, negligence and abuse do occur and guardians do make unwise decisions but there are provisions to cope with such situation. She may request the legal authorities to annul any contract concluded against her will or which falls short of her expectations.

11.0 WHETHER ABSENCE OF GUARDIAN IN MARRIAGE CONTRACT CAN RENDER THE MARRIAGE INVALID

There is no consensus among the Muslim Jurists whether or not Guardian is necessary in marriage contract such that its absence will vitiate the marriage itself. Maliki and Shafi'i School are of the view that there is no marriage contract unless there is a Waliy. However, according to Imam Abu Hanifah, Zufuri, Shaabal and Zhuri where a woman conducts a marriage contract without Waliy, this will not invalidate the marriage in as much there is Kafa'a among these spouses, otherwise it is invalid. However, Imam Daud make a distinction between a spinster and widow or divorcee. He opined that for spinster, it is necessary to have guardian in her marriage contract, and for a Divorcee and widow requirement of Waliy is just a formality which need not to be achieved.

Another opinion attributed to Ibn-Qasim who related it to Maliki about Guardianship, is that the requirement of Guardianship is Sunnah (favourable) rather than Fard (obligation) such that the right to inheritance exists between the spouses who contract their marriage without Waliy. Those who have the view that Waliy is not necessary in marriage contract opined that guardianship is just a formality not a requirement the absence of which will not negate the marriage contract.

The basis of their distinction on these views of Waliy is that there is a Qur'anic injunction and or a Hadith that the requirement of Waliy is necessary in a marriage Contract. In essence all the authorities that talk about Waliy in marriage contract do not admit one meaning or direct translation to make it compulsory. Equally of importance is the fact that most of the Hadith that talk about requirement of Waliy in addition to it being capable of carrying more than one meaning, jurists are not unanimous about their authenticity.

Some of these authorities are:

- a. Q2:232: The jurists hold the view that this verse is addressed to Waliy Guardian. Had they not have right to Guardianship over their wards they would not have been ordered to refrain from refusing to allow their wards to go back to their Husband?
- b. Q2:221: This in accordance to the jurist, is addresses to Guardians. In the Hadith, they relied on the hadith of Zuhr related to Urwatu from Aisha
- c. Q2:234, Q2:232 and Q2:230: *“Those who on the other hand opined that guardian is not necessary in the marriage contract from Qur’an and hadith relied on these verses”.*

These evident that women are given the right to marry themselves out without Waliy.

Having examined the position of the jurist on whether or not Waliy is necessary in Marriage Contract, let us now proceed to other jurisdiction with a view to seeing how their law of personal status is codified.

12.0 GUARDIANSHIP IN MARRIAGE AND THE ISLAMIC CODE OF PERSONAL STATUS OF OTHER JURISDICTIONS

Under Muslim law, any person who has attained puberty is entitled to act in all matters affecting his or her status or his or her property. But the law has been materially altered by the Indian Majority Act, 1875 and the only matter in which, a Muslim is now entitled to act after attaining puberty are Marriage and Divorce, and in all other matters, a minority can continue to enjoy until the attaining the age of 18. Until then, the court has power to appoint a guardian for his person or his property or both under the guardian’s and Ward Act, 1890. In which case, the age of minority is prolonged until the minor has completed the age of 21 years,²⁷ every Muslim who is of sound mind and has attained the age of puberty is competent to contract a valid marriage through their respective guardian²⁸ under Muslim law, and the ages prescribed for different matters are different.

A minor is a person who has not attained the age of the majority. The age of the majority is not the same in all the matters. Puberty and majority are one and the same²⁹ in matters relating to marriage, divorce and adoption. A person shall be deemed to be a minor till the age of puberty under Sunni law, no male is said to have attained puberty under the age of 12

²⁷Ibn Rush (supra) g7,8-9

²⁸ Ahmad A, Mohammedan Law, 2nd edition 2004, p129 central law agency, Allahabad.

²⁹ DR. Purohit No, The Principles of Muhammeden law, 2nd edition 1998 pg. 115 orient publishing Company, Allahabad (ibid p. 530)

years and no female under the age of 9 years³⁰ but in the absence of any evidence to the contrary, a male or a female is presumed to have attained puberty at the age of 15 years. According to Shia law, the age of puberty for a male is 15 years and for a female is 9 years. Puberty begins with mensuration which presumed to commence between the ages of 9 and 10. ³¹ The age of puberty is an age at which a person is supposed to acquire the sexual experience.³²

Before passing of the Indian Majority Act of 1875, the age of majority of Hindus and Muslim was determined on the basis of the provisions of their respective personal laws. Persons other than Hindus and Muslims were governed by the rule of English law. Consequently, the law was modified by local Acts and regulations Act of 1793 was passed, to the effect that both Hindus and Muslims were limited to the expiration of the fifteen years.³³

This limit was later on raised to 18 years. In Bombay, there was the Bombay minor Act (XX of 1864) and Madras Regulation Act V of 1804³⁴. There was also Act IX of 1861 which was applicable to the whole of British. Indian and the European British Minor Act (XIII of 1874) was applicable to persons born in United Kingdom. Under the Indian Christian marriage Act of 1872, the age of majority is 21 years,³⁵ on account of these uncertainties the Indian majority Act 1875 was passed. However, as regard to the matter of marriage dower, divorce and adoption, the Hindus and Muslims were governed by their own laws. According to this Act, a person of the age between 18 and 21 could personally enter into contract notwithstanding the provision of section ii of the Indian contract Act of 1872.³⁶

13.0 REPUDIATION

We have seen in the previous work that where a minor was contracted in marriage by his father or grandfather, he has no right to repudiate the marriage on attaining puberty unless the contract manifested imminent disadvantage against the minor or has been fraudulent or negligently entered into.

³⁰DrPurohit N. (Supra) pg 317

³¹ Ibid pg 530

³²Verma B. Islami law 6th Ed 1986 P.318 law publishes (indian) private Limited

³³WWW.Madinamosque (supra)

³⁴ ibid

³⁵ Dr. Qureshi M. Muslim Law 2nd Edition 2002 p. 126 central law Publication, Allahsaba.

³⁶WWW.Madinamosques (supra)

i. REPUDIATION BY A MALE MINOR

A male minor on attaining puberty has a right of repudiating the marriage when he is given in marriage by his father or Grandfather only if the father or grandfather has acted:

- a. Carelessly;
- b. Negligently;
- c. Fraudulently; or
- d. Wickedly.³⁷

Thus if a minor is married to a lunatic, impotent or idiot, such marriage may be repudiated by the minor only after he attains Majority,³⁸ the right of repudiation may be exercised on attaining majority, unless ratified.³⁹

ii. REPUDIATION BY A FEMALE MINOR

Before passing of Muslim Marriage Act of 1939, a female minor if given in marriage by her father or grandfather could not repudiate such marriage in any circumstance⁴⁰. However, if she is given in marriage by her guardian, she had the right of repudiating the marriage.⁴¹ But the courts in India, allowed this in numerous account, this can be seen in the case of Aziz Bano V. Moh'd Ibrahim,⁴² where the court held that a Shia girl given in marriage by her father to a sunni male, has right of repudiating such marriage on getting puberty, unless she has ratified it impliedly by consummation or otherwise, she has the right of repudiation because such marriage would be repugnant to her religious setting.⁴³

In Ghulam Sakina V. Falak Sher⁴⁴, it was held that where the marriage of a female minor was solemnized and consummated before she attained the age of 15 years, it did not amount to consummation within the meaning of section 2 (VII) of the dissolution of Marriage Act 1939.

³⁷ Dr. Quershi M. (supar) P. 128

³⁸ Ibid 229,

³⁹ ibid

⁴⁰ Aziz Bano Vs Muhammad Ibrahim ALR 1925 All 720

⁴¹ WWW.Madinamosques (supra)

⁴² ibid

⁴³ Supra

⁴⁴ AIR. 1950 Lah 45

However, a minor is allowed to exercise this option of puberty (khyar-ul-bulugh) under the dissolution of Muslim marriage Act of 1939 and some certain conditions must exist, these are as follows:

- i. The option should be exercised immediately on attaining puberty
- ii. The marriage should not have been consummated.⁴⁵

14.0 REFORM OF MUSLIM FAMILY LAW IN OTHER JURISDICTIONS

The temporary Jordan Legislation of 2001 reinstates court scrutiny over Guardians action in marrying a ward below the age of legal majority.

Iraq amendment to its 1959 law is one of the clearest and most detailed in this respect, detailing in three separate clauses, prohibiting forceful marriage and imposes criminal penalties on those doing so. Algerian law also explicitly forbids the wakil from forcing his ward into the marriage or marrying the ward without the latter's consent.⁴⁶ In 2005 Mufti in Saudi Arabia where there is no codification, declared that it was unlawful for fathers to force their daughters into an unwanted marriage.⁴⁷

Another issue remaining in the statutory law around the other aspects of guardianship in marriage is whether a woman of full legal majority needs her guardian's consent to her marriage. Some laws continue to require that a woman's guardian concludes the contract on her behalf, rather than the woman doing in person. Where this is the case clearly the woman's marriage is dependent upon the consent of the guardian is required to conclude the contract.⁴⁸

However, the Moroccan Law allows a woman to conclude her own contract of marriage in person. This option is allowed for any woman of legal majority by its 2004 law⁴⁹ In 2005 the Algeria legislators finally allowed an adult woman to conclude her marriage contract in the presence of a guardian who is her father or relative or any other person of her choice.

⁴⁵WWW.Madinamosques (supra)

⁴⁶ Lynn Welchman (supra)

⁴⁷ibid

⁴⁸ ibid

⁴⁹ Ibid

Kuwait's 2004 amendment to its 1984 Law exceptionally allows a previously married woman to ask the judge to conclude the contract of her remarriage to her former husband.⁵⁰

From the above, it is understood that, unlike in Nigeria where there is a codification, some foreign countries went further to legislate on the issue of Guardianship, thereby delimiting the power of Wali mujbir and consider the choice of the ward. It is equally important to highlight that women are even allowed in those jurisdictions to conclude their marriage contract personally with or without a Wali. The judicial attitude of those jurisdictions gives effect to those laws for example India. It is highly likely that Nigeria too will one day follow in the footsteps of these countries thereby codifying its law of Personal Status.

15.0 CONCLUSION

Conclusively, we have seen how the paper examines in great detail the requirements of a Guardian in Islamic Marriage contract. The juristic views in that regard and an insight into the coercive guardian and the views of the Ulama. In summary, the paper ventured into other jurisdictions whose Islamic Law of Personal Status are codified. We have also seen the judicial attitude of the courts in those countries with particular reference to India.

In carrying out the research the writers adopted an arm chair methodology without going to any field. The writers adopted both doctrinal and non-doctrinal research methodology.

The writers have the following recommendations:

- i. It is highly recommended that marriage guardianship under Islamic Law in Nigeria be codified in a legislation by State Houses of Assembly of Muslim majority states.
- ii. The law, if enacted, should provide a clear cut definition and the specific qualities required of a guardian in Islamic marriage, hierarchical structure in accordance with the Maliki Law applicable in Nigeria Courts.
- iii. The powers and limitation of a guardian should be clearly spelt out in the attendant punishment for its breach in the law.

⁵⁰ ibid

- iv. It is highly recommended that a lady who is matured should be allowed to choose her guardian among those allowed by the law.
- v. It is essential that Emirs, District Heads, Village Heads should be given powers to act as guardians, but their decisions should be subjected to a judicial review by a competent sharia court in Nigeria.

It is the writers hope that Nigeria will one day join those countries that codified their laws of Personal Status there by creating a legal regime that will check the excessive powers of coercive guardians.